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D4.2 - REPORT ON IMPROVED NEMATODE DNA-METABARCODING TOOL FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF NEMATODE COMMUNITY COMPOSITION AND DIVERSITY

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Summary

Terrestrial nematode communities are often applied as bioindicators to assess soil health. However, their morphological characterisation is limited for taxonomic experts only and molecular tools applicable for non-nematode specialist are currently under development. During WP4, EV-ILVO investigated a couple of aspects for a more accurate application of DNA-metabarcoding for the characterization of nematode communities from soil samples. As a result, the following objectives were achieved. Firstly, an expanded and curated database of 18S rRNA nematode sequences was constructed. Secondly, different bio-informatics pipelines were compared and the one most efficient for reliable nematode taxon assignment was selected. Thirdly, DNA-extraction from nematode suspensions derived from soil samples was optimized. Fourthly, insights to improve the quantitative aspect of DNA-metabarcoding were revealed. Although efforts are continued to further increase the quality of the established nematode DNA-metabarcoding protocol, it can be concluded that the technique is more than ever ready to replace the time-consuming morphological characterization of nematode communities for soil health assessments.

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Introduction

Compared with successful restoration events of above-ground ecosystems, restoration activities for soil ecosystems is still very limited. This is not only due to the restricted functional knowledge on soil ecosystems, it is also because of lack of effective soil biodiversity assessment methods (Lehmann et al., 2020). Thus, as a first step, there is a considerable need for high-throughput and reliable monitoring methods to aid the development of strategies for restoration, sustainable use and protection of (agricultural) soils. Assessment of soil health comprising the level of biodiversity and ecosystem services through complete analysis of the soil food web containing bacteria, fungi, nematodes, mites, insects, Collembola, earthworms etc. is technically daunting and immensely time consuming. Alternatively, selected biotic indicators, which reflect the structure and function of ecological processes and responds to natural or anthropic changes in soil conditions, can be used. Nematodes or roundworms are believed to be promising bio-indicators (Griffiths et al., 2016).

Nematodes are among the most diverse eukaryotes which vary in sensitivity to pollutants and environmental disturbances (Bongers & Ferris, 1999) therefore receiving increased attention as biological indicators to monitor soil biodiversity and ecosystem functioning (Mekonen et al., 2017; Moura & Franzener, 2017; Gao et al, 2020). Obtained knowledge about nematode feeding types and life-history strategies have led to the development of several nematode community indices as a qualitative and quantitative assessment system for soil health (Bongers, 1990; Bongers & Ferris, 1999; Ferris et al., 2001; Gao et al., 2020; Tsiafouli & Sgardelis, 2017). However, the characterization of nematode communities is still primarily based on morphological and morphometrical measurements using microscopy. This requires a high level of expertise. Also it is time-consuming and therefore traditional morphological analyses of nematode suspensions extracted from a soil sample containing easily a few thousands of individuals, is mostly restricted to 100-250 individuals (de la Peña et al., 2016; Gao et al, 2020; Herren et al., 2020; Leroy et al., 2009). This restriction potentially causes biased results regarding species richness and abundance. Luckily, the ability to characterize soil nematode diversity has recently been expanded by the use of next generation sequencing (NGS) based metabarcoding techniques. However, since its introduction, DNA-metabarcoding (or amplicon sequencing) has been used mainly for the characterization of one-cellular micro-organisms. So far, relatively few research groups have used high-throughput DNA-metabarcoding to analyze nematode communities (Darby et al., 2013; Holovachov et al., 2017; Porazinska et al., 2009; Waeyenberge et al., 2019). This is probably due to the novelty of the method, and the technical challenges associated as the development of reliable protocols requires the combination of molecular, nematological and bioinformatics know-how.

Metabarcoding uses multiplex identifiers for sample-specific labelling of nucleic acids which allows analyzing hundreds of samples in a single instrument run, extending DNA-based species identification from individuals to communities (Taberlet et al., 2012). This technique is very promising as it has several advantages: (i) the method is very sensitive and likely to outperform traditional methods in speed, accuracy, and resolution of species identification (Ji et al., 2013); (ii) the technique is cost-

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efficient and (iii) has the potential to enable a global network of biodiversity surveillance and monitoring with minimal effect on the environment (Alsos et al., 2018; Bohmann et al., 2014). Few years ago, EV-ILVO initiated research to establish robust methodologies based on the use of DNA-metabarcoding to replace current microscopic nematode identification methods (Waeyenberge et al., 2019). Unfortunately, methodological challenges remained. Firstly, for biomonitoring of the environment with DNA-metabarcoding it is essential to ascertain an accurate taxonomic classification of sequences recovered through DNA-metabarcoding (Hleap et al., 2020). The accuracy is affected by both the taxonomic assignment method and the reference database used. Public sequence database are available (www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/index-e.html, www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home and www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/), however, DNA sequences from a number of nematode genera and species are still missing or many entries are unidentified, mislabelled, or refer to outdated, even misspelled taxon names. Several taxonomic assignment programs exist, however, it is unclear which of these methods are most suitable for nematode characterisation. Secondly, DNA-extraction techniques are not optimized for extraction of nematode DNA from a very diverse community or origin. Thirdly, determination of the relative abundance of different nematode taxa by DNA metabarcoding is unreliable.

One of the specific objectives of WP4 is to implement and further optimize assays for nematode biodiversity determination in soils via the application of DNA-metabarcoding. To achieve this objective, the previously mentioned challenges will be addressed: (i) expanding the nematode sequence database by isolation and combined pheno- and genotypic characterisation of a number of nematode species or genera and by browsing and controlling existing nematode sequence databases; (ii) evaluating bio-informatics pipelines with special attention for taxonomic assignment methods; (iii) optimizing the DNA extraction method based on tests with natural nematode communities spiked with a cultured nematode species; (iv) exploring the inclusion of correction factors for accurate quantification of different nematode taxa. This Deliverable (D4.2) reports on the results of these investigations.

1 Nematode sequence taxonomic assignment

1.1 Introduction

The taxonomic assignment methods can generally be classified in four major strategies: sequence similarity, sequence composition, phylogenetics, and probabilistics (Hleap et al., 2020). Sequence similarity methods rely merely on alignments between the query and reference sequences using various measures of similarity (Holovachov et al., 2017). Sequence composition methods build models based on compositional features (e.g. k-mers) to assign taxonomic ranks for each read (Hleap et al., 2020). Phylogenetic approaches utilize phylogeny inference algorithms to either perform a *de novo* phylogeny or use a reference guiding tree for the placement of query reads across all nodes in the reference topology (Hleap et al., 2020; Holovachov et al., 2017). Probabilistic methods (e.g. Likelihood, Bayesian) rely on probability estimates to place a query sequence to a particular taxon (Holovachov et al., 2017). Taxonomic classification of representative sequences varies considerably among these methods. Although not meant to be exhaustive, this study provides a benchmark of eight taxonomic assignment tools based on several of these methodologies.

Independently of all technical innovations, metabarcoding will always rely on a good and reliable taxonomic reference database (Macher et al., 2017). GenBank is one of the main public repositories of DNA barcode sequences. Although the actual overall data quality is much better than often assumed (Leray et al., 2019), yet many sequences comprise entries with wrong or misleading species attributions (Bridge et al., 2003; Liu et al., 2020). The Barcode of Life Data Systems (BOLD) is also one of the main repositories for DNA barcode data for animals, plants, and fungi. Specimen records in BOLD will only gain formal barcode status until seven data elements are in place: 1) (interim) species name, 2) voucher data (catalogue number and institution storing), 3) collection record, 4) identifier of the specimen, 5) sequence of at least 500 bp, 6) primer information, and 7) trace files for the sequence data (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007). However, no curation of the nematode taxonomy, neither an evaluation of the true identity of the specimen records is performed in BOLD itself. Correct taxonomic assignments depend on the quality and completeness of the sequence reference database used to characterize the community composition (Arranz et al., 2020) and this database should be taxonomically curated for the reference sequences of the targeted gene. Valuable examples of such databases are available for fungi with the database UNITE (Abarenkov et al., 2010), for Bacteria and Archaea with the databases SILVA (Pruesse et al., 2007) and GreenGenes (DeSantis et al., 2006), and for protists with the database EukRef (Kolisko et al., 2020). Although no curated database exists for nematodes, there is a good first attempt to provide a nematode reference database for the ITS2 DNA region (Workentine et al., 2020), but this database doesn't support any other marker regions and there is no quality control for mislabeled taxa yet. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a real curated reference database for nematodes, especially for the commonly used 18S barcode region.

This study provides a benchmark of 8 taxonomic assignment tools based on mock community data and provides a custom NCBI 18S rRNA region nematode sequence database as a reference database which is compared to SILVA.

1.2 Material and Methods

1.2.1 Quality control, merging, and denoising pipeline

Mock communities were prepared as in Waeyenberge et al. (2019). The mock communities were analysed using identical filtering, merging, and clustering or denoising steps to guarantee unbiased benchmarking. Primer sequences were removed from the obtained reads using Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014), followed by removal of the adapters using Cutadapt v3.3 (Martin, 2011) and merging of the reads with PEAR v0.9.11 (Zhang et al., 2014). For the mock communities, both an OTU table and ASV table was created for comparison using VSEARCH v2.17.0 (Rognes et al., 2016) and DADA2 v1.18 (Callahan et al., 2016) respectively. The obtained OTU and ASV tables are then used for subsequent analyses with the different taxonomic assignment methods.

1.2.2 Assembly of reference databases

A custom 18S nematode sequence database was built from available sequence entries retrieved from the NCBI database GenBank, hereafter called the NCBI database. The obtained sequences were aligned using SINA v.1.7.1 against a reference alignment obtained from SILVA SSU 138 where only nematode sequences were retained. Sequences that were labelled with either 'uncultured', 'environmental', 'unidentified', 'NA' or 'cf._' were removed with seqkit v.0.10.1. and divergent (--remove_divergent_minperc 0.6) and short (<600bp) sequences were removed using CIALign v.1.0.9. Sequences were labelled with the proper taxonomy retrieved preferably from WORMS and if not available from the NCBI taxonomy using a custom script. To improve taxonomy, SATIVA was used to identify taxonomically mislabeled sequences (Kozlov et al., 2016). To remove additional mislabeled sequences, a phylogeny was produced with FastTree version 2.1.11 and manually inspected.

Newly retrieved nematode sequences were also obtained as follows: nematode individuals were isolated from nematode suspensions extracted from soil samples by zonal centrifugation (Hendrickx, 1995) and identified by microscopic analysis. To allow subsequent verification of the identification, a voucher was included, containing images or videos of each barcoded specimen. Two primer sets amplifying overlapping parts of the 18S rRNA gene (Holterman et al., 2006) were used to amplify the 18S rRNA gene.

For comparison, another reference database was constructed from SILVA with nematode sequences extracted from the SILVA 138 release ("SILVA_138_SSURef_Nr99.fasta") (Quast et al., 2012) from which only sequences belonging to the phylum Nematoda were retained. Using a custom script, the NCBI taxonomy was retrieved for each sequence entry to obtain a full and consistent classification.

1.2.3 Taxonomic assignment methods

Eight different taxonomic assignment methods were compared. Metaxa2 v.2.2 (Bengtsson-Palme et al., 2018), which is based on a combination of hidden Markov models (HMMs) and sequence alignments, was used with two different thresholds (default 80% and 10%). Kraken2 v.2.0.8-beta (Wood et al., 2019), which uses k-mers to classify sequences, was used with the default settings. The RDP classifier (Wang et al., 2007), a naïve Bayesian classifier implemented in the R-package of DADA2 v.1.18, was used with the default settings. The IDTaxa algorithm (Murali et al., 2018), implemented in the R-package DECIPHER v.2.16.1 and which employs principles of machine learning, was used with two different thresholds settings (60% (default) and 10%). The QIIME2 v.2020.6.0 plugin q2-feature-classifier, which implements a scikit-learn naïve Bayes machine-learning classifier (Bokulich et al., 2018), was used with the default settings. ObiTools3 v.3.0.0b38, which assigns sequences to a taxon based on sequence similarity, was used with a threshold of 90%. The TAG.ME software, which uses random forest models, was slightly modified to be able to handle reference databases with only one taxon order, and was used with the default threshold settings. To classify the sequences using EPA-ng, the reference database is aligned against a reference alignment from nematode sequences extracted from SILVA SSU 138 using SINA. A phylogenetic tree is constructed for the reference database with FastTree v.2.1.10 using the GTR-GAMMA model. The query reads are then aligned against the aligned reference database using SINA. Finally, EPA-ng v.0.3.6 (Barbera et al., 2018) is run with default settings using 10 threads.

1.2.4 Analysis and visualisation of the results

The phyloseq R package 1.36.0 was used to visualize the taxonomic composition resulting from the different taxonomic pipelines. Results were plotted in R and the F1-score was used as a combined metric of both precision and recall for each taxonomic classification method. Taxa that were observed by a taxonomic assigned method that were also present according to the morphological data, represent true positives (TP), taxa not observed by the taxonomic assignment method but observed with the morphological data, represent false negatives (FN) and taxa observed by the taxonomic assignment methods but not observed in the morphological data, are false positives (FP). The F1-score is calculated as follows:

$$FDR = \frac{FP}{(FP + TP)}$$

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}$$

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}$$

$$F1 - score = 2 * \frac{TPR * PPV}{TPR + PPV}$$

1.3 Results and discussion

1.3.1 Curated nematode 18S rRNA sequence database

We have assembled an 'in house' curated 18S rRNA nematode sequence database based on available nematode sequences in public repositories. The database currently contains more than 5000 sequences belonging to 758 genera and 1676 species. Sixty-four sequences (Table A1) were newly retrieved after morphological identification of nematode individuals each followed by 18S rRNA sequencing. The latter is limited due to the restricted access to lab facilities during the COVID-19 measurements. However, during and even beyond the project duration, it is planned to continuously expand this database taking advantage of sample surveys and other activities.

1.3.2 Characterization of the mock communities

Eight taxonomic classification methods were evaluated at genus level with two different reference databases using two mock communities. As illustrated in figure 1 and figure 2, none of the methods gave the same results. Metaxa2 (threshold 80%), Obitoools3 and QIIME2 are more conserved in assigning taxa at genus level. When the threshold for Metaxa2 was lowered, more taxa could be assigned for the SILVA database. When the NCBI database was used, most ASVs and OTUs could already be assigned with the default settings.

For the NCBI database, fewer taxa could be assigned with the RDP classifier and IDTAXA. These difference are found for taxa belonging to the Dorylaimida. For QIIME2, more ASVs could be assigned when the NCBI database was used.

Figure 1. Relative abundances obtained with the different taxonomic assignment methods using the SILVA database. The mock community represents the real situation.

1.3.3 Comparison of the morphological data with the metabarcoding data for each method using the SILVA database

Figure 3 shows the results of the taxonomic assignment method using the SILVA database with the morphological data. In general, when using ASVs, in one of the samples, *Oscheius* could not be identified by any of the methods. Except for the taxon *Oscheius* in one samples, no differences were observed between the assignment of OTUs and ASVs for Kraken2, EPA-ng, obitools3, QIIME2 and IDTAXA with default settings.

Metaxa2 retrieved only few taxa with default settings (threshold 80%) and was not able to assign *Mesorhabditis*, *Heterorhabditis*, *Ditylenchus* and *Acrobelloides* for both ASVs and OTUs and for ASVs only was unable to retrieve *Plectus* in all samples. Because only few taxa could be recovered, the threshold was lowered to 10% for comparison. At 10%, most taxa could be recovered, although we cannot excluded some taxa might be false positives as we did not identify the dorylaimid below order level.

Benchmarking taxonomic assignment methods – custom NCBI database

Figure 2. Relative abundances obtained with the different taxonomic assignment methods using the NCBI database. The mock community represents the real situation.

Kraken2 was able to assign all species for both ASVs and OTUs except for *Ditylenchus*.

EPA-ng was unable to assign *Plectus* and *Acrobeloides*, all other taxa could be assigned.

Similarly, Obitools3 could not assign *Plectus* and *Acrobeloides* and remarkably it's the only method that did not assign any dorylaimid taxon.

Except for *Acrobeloides*, QIIME2 was able to retrieve all the taxa for both ASVs and OTUs.

TAG.ME misassigned *Anguina* (false positive) which is closely related to *Ditylenchus*, which was not retrieved by this method. Also *Oscheius* could not be assigned by TAG.ME. Also differences in assignments could be identified between OTUs and ASVs, for the OTUs one more dorylaimid taxon was assigned, namely *Discolaimus* and *Tylencholaimus* was found in more samples for the OTUs.

The RDP classifier was able to assign all taxa when ASVs were used, but was unable to identify *Mesorhabditis* with the OTUs. One more dorylaimid taxon (*Ecumenicus*) was assigned for the OTUs compared with the ASVs.

Figure 3. Comparison of absence/presence data for taxa assigned by the taxonomic assignment method using the SILVA database with the morphological data.

IDTAXA was unable to identify *Ditylenchus* and *Acrobeloides* at default settings. For comparison, when the threshold was lowered to 10%, IDTAXA was able to assign *Ditylenchus* when using OTUs but falsely assign it as *Subanguina* (a closely related taxon of *Ditylenchus*) when using ASVs. Also one more dorylaimid taxon (*Allodorylaimus*) for some sample with ASVs and all samples with OTUs was assigned compared to the results when using the default settings.

1.3.4 Comparison of the morphological data with the metabarcoding data for each method using the in-house curated custom NCBI database

Figure 4 shows the results of the taxonomic assignment method using the custom NCBI database. As for the results with the SILVA database, in one of the samples *Oscheius* could not be identified by any of the methods. Except for unassigned *Oscheius* in one sample with ASVs, no differences were observed between the assignment of OTUs and ASVs for Kraken2, Obitools3, QIIME2, TAG.ME and IDTAXA with default settings.

Metaxa2 was able to assign all taxa with the use of the NCBI database, also with default settings. When the threshold for the reliability of the assignment was lowered to 10%, one more dorylaimid was recovered (*Mesodorylaimus*) in some sample for the ASVs and in all samples for the OTUs.

As when using the SILVA database, Kraken2 recovered all taxa except *Ditylenchus*.

Figure 4. Comparison of absence/presence data for taxa assigned by the taxonomic assignment method using the custom NCBI database with the morphological data.

EPA-ng was unable to assign *Plectus* and *Acrobeloides* when using ASVs. Also when using ASVs, in some sample the dorylaimid taxon *Calcaridorylaimus* was assigned, a taxon that was not recovered when using OTUs. When using OTUs, all taxa could be recovered.

Obitools3 could not assign *Plectus* and *Acrobeloides* as with the SILVA database and also no dorylaimid taxon was recovered.

QIIME2 was unable to recover *Plectus* and *Heterorhabditis*.

TAG.ME was able to recover all taxa except for *Pratylenchus*.

All taxa were recovered with the RDP classifier. For some samples, the dorylaimid *Aporcelaimellus* was not recovered when using ASVs in comparison with OTUs.

IDTAXA could not assign *Acrobeloides* for both ASVs and OTUs and additionally could not assign *Plectus* with the default threshold of 60%. When the threshold was lowered to 10% for comparison, all taxa present in the mock community could be retrieved. For OTUs, the dorylaimid *Oxydirus* was recovered in all samples while only assigned in three sample for the ASVs.

1.3.5 Evaluation of the F1-score to assess the accuracy of the different taxonomic assignment methods

The F1-score was evaluated at the genus level (Figure 5) and family level (Figure 6) as these are the key taxonomic ranks for nematode-based functional diversity analysis and biological monitoring. We excluded the taxon belonging to the Dorylaimida from the F1-score calculations as we were unable to identify this taxon with neither morphology and phylogeny with good confidence.

The RDP classifier as implemented in the DADA2 function assignTaxonomy generated the highest average F1-score among the tested methods at genus level with an average value of 0.98 (0.024 standard deviation) for all tested combinations (ASV vs OTU and NCBI vs SILVA). The RDP classifier had a higher F1-score when ASVs were used (average F1-score 0.99, standard deviation 0.018) in comparison to OTUs (average F1-score of 0.97, standard deviation 0.027). For the OTUs, a higher F1-score was obtained in combination with the NCBI database (average F1-score 1, standard deviation 0) in comparison with the SILVA database (average F1-score 0.95, standard deviation 0). At family level, all taxa could be identified using both reference database and ASVs and OTUs.

Figure 5. F1-score for each method at genus level.

The RDP classifier was followed by kraken2 with an average F1-score of 0.94 (0.014 standard deviation) (Figure 5.). The average F1-score was slightly higher when OTUs were used (average F1-score 0.95, standard deviation 0) in comparison to ASVs (average F1-score 0.94, standard deviation 0.020). At family level the F1-score was on average 1 (Figure 6).

Metaxa2 has an average F1-score of 0.92 (0.132 standard deviation) at genus level (Figure 5). With default settings, the F1-score using the SILVA database was rather low with an average F1-score of 0.65 (0.034 standard deviation) for ASVs and an average F1-score of 0.75 (0 standard deviation) for

OTUs. When the threshold for the Metaxa2 assignment accuracy was lowered to 10%, the F1-score became 0.99 (0.019 standard deviation) when using ASVs and 1 (0 standard deviation) when using OTUs. With the NCBI database using the default threshold for Metaxa2, the average F1-score was 0.99 (0.019 standard deviation) for the ASVs and 1 (0 standard deviation) for the OTUs and the F1-score did not change by lowering the threshold to 10% (Figure 5). At family level (Figure 6), the NCBI database performed better with an average F1-score of 1 (0 standard deviation) for both the ASVs and OTUs. The F1-score for the SILVA database at family level was 0.95 (0.053 standard deviation).

Metaxa2 was closely followed by QIIME2 with an average F1-score of 0.91 (0.034 standard deviation). QIIME2 performed better when the SILVA database was used with an average F1-score of 0.94 (0.021 standard deviation) for ASVs and 0.95 (0 standard deviation) for OTUs. F1-scores for the NCBI database are 0.88 (0.023 standard deviation) for ASVs and 0.89 (0 standard deviation) for OTUs. At family level, QIIME2 performed better when the SILVA database was used with an average F1-score of 1 (0 standard deviation) for both OTUs and ASVs. The average F1-score when the NCBI database was used was 0.94 (0 standard deviation).

Figure 6. F1-score for each method at family level.

IDTAXA also had an average F1-score of 0.91 (0.058 standard deviation). For ASVs, the F1-score was 0.88 (0.023 standard deviation) for both the NCBI and SILVA database when using the default 60% threshold. When the threshold was lowered to 10% for the ASVs, the NCBI database scored better with an average F1-score of 0.99 (0.019 standard deviation) in comparison to an F1-score of 0.89 (0.020 standard deviation) for the SILVA database. For the OTUs, the SILVA database scored better both at the default threshold with an F1-score of 0.89 (0.052 standard deviation) in comparison with an average F1-score of 0.82 (0 standard deviation) for the NCBI database and at lowered threshold of 10% with an F1-score of 1 (0 standard deviation) in comparison to an F1-score of 0.9 (0 standard

deviation) for the NCBI database. At family level, the F1-score was 1 for both thresholds used and no differences could be observed between the two databases.

TAG.ME had an average F1-score of 0.89 (0.053 standard deviation). The NCBI database performed overall better than the SILVA database at genus level with an F1-score of 0.94 (0.021 standard deviation) for the ASVs and 0.95 (0 standard deviation) for the OTUs. The average F1-score for the SILVA database was 0.89 (0 standard deviation) for both ASVs and OTUs. At family level, the average F1-score was 1 for both databases and ASVs and OTUs.

EPA-ng had an average F1-score of 0.88 (0.077 standard deviation). EPA-ng performed better when the NCBI database was used with an average F1-score of 0.88 (0.023 standard deviation) against an average F1-score of 0.81 (0.026 standard deviation) with the SILVA database for the ASVs and an F1-score of 1 (0 standard deviation) for the NCBI database against an average F1-score of 0.82 (0 standard deviation) with the SILVA database for the OTUs. At the family level, the F1-score was higher when the NCBI database was used with an average F1-score of 0.94 (0 standard deviation) for the ASVs and 1 (0 standard deviation) for the OTUs. The average F1-score for the SILVA database was 0.8 (0 standard deviation) for both OTUs and ASVs.

Obitools3 had the lowest average F1-score at genus level with an average of 0.85 (0.038 standard deviation). The F1-score was higher with use of the NCBI database with an F1-score of 0.89 (0.023 standard deviation) for ASVs and 0.89 (0 standard deviation) for OTUs. Obitools3 had an F1-score of 0.81 (0.026 standard deviation) for the ASVs and 0.82 (0 standard deviation) for the OTUs. At family level, it performed better than EPA-ng. Obitools3 had slightly better results for ASVs when the NCBI database was used with an F1-score of 0.97 (0.031 standard deviation). For the OTUs with the NCBI database and both OTUs and ASVs with the SILVA database the F-score was 0.94 (0 standard deviation).

1.3.6 Evaluation on real nematode communities

The taxonomic assignment methods were also tested on a real dataset of 8 samples. As illustrated in Figure 7, the composition of the nematode communities found through metabarcoding depends on the method of choice. As the real nematode community is not known for these environmental samples, we cannot benchmark the methods based on this data. Yet, as an example of how a method can influence the downstream analysis, it can be observed that for example QIIME2 is unable to assign members of the Cephalobidae (eg. *Pseudoacrobeles*, *Chiloplacus*, *Eucephalobus*, *Acrobeles*, *Acrobeloides* and *Cephalobus*) for most of the samples, while other methods did assign at least one member of this family in most samples. The opposite is also true for some methods that assigned taxa while most other methods did not assign that specific taxon in most samples. For example Obitools3 assigned *Prodesmodora* and EPA-ng assigned *Procamallarus* and *Sabatieria* in multiple sample while other methods did not assign ASVs to these taxa.

Figure 7. Overview of absence/presence data according to the different taxonomic assignment methods plotted in relation to the nematode classification ranks.

2 Nematode community DNA extraction

2.1 Introduction

There are many commercial DNA extraction kits that are capable of extracting high-quality DNA directly from soil but such methods have common disadvantages. They can only handle limited amounts of soil (5-10 grams) and a large part of the isolated DNA is unwanted DNA (DNA from untargeted soil organisms, from plant material, etc.). On the other hand, nematodes can easily be separated from soil particles, other soil-dwelling organisms and plant parts applying different extraction methods (McSorley & Walter, 1991; Hendrickx, 1995; Viglierchio & Schmitt, 1983). The benefit of this “technical enrichment procedure” is that a lot of non-nematode soil organisms and soil chemical substances that potentially can inhibit subsequent enzymatic steps (like PCR) are already removed before the actual DNA-extraction. Moreover, this enrichment method makes it possible to apply a DNA-extraction method on a nematode suspension derived from a larger amount of soil (100 mL). Therefore, at EV-ILVO, it was decided to always first extract the nematodes from a soil sample before proceeding with the DNA-extraction method itself.

Obtained nematode suspensions are concentrated to make the volume suitable for DNA-extraction with a commercial DNA-extraction kit. At EV-ILVO, nematodes are concentrated passively by gravity force till a volume of 2-5 mL. This is a multi-step procedure taking several days and in which in each step a smaller recipient is used after removing part of the supernatant. In an attempt to speed up the process, centrifugation was applied to actively concentrate the nematodes. However, replacing the gravity-method by centrifugation, didn't give satisfactory results. A number of nematodes remained in the suspension and got lost during removal of the supernatant. Moreover, still several steps were needed to reduce the volume, again using different, smaller-sized recipients in each step. During transferring the re-suspended nematode pellet into a smaller recipient, nematodes got lost because nematodes have the tendency to stick to the edges of the material used.

It was demonstrated that the applied DNA-extraction method (an enzymatic lysis method with Proteinase K) didn't release DNA of certain nematode genera (Waeyenberge et al., 2019). The cuticle protects the nematode and although its basic structure is generally the same, its composition differs (Bird, 1971). Probably this has an effect on DNA-extraction efficiency.

Therefore, other methods to concentrate the nematode suspension and another DNA-extraction method based on chemical lysis was tested to investigate whether it was possible to improve efficiency and sensitivity of the DNA-extraction procedure for nematode suspensions.

2.2 Material and Methods

2.2.1 Zonal centrifugation

At EV-ILVO, 90-95% of all nematodes present in a 100 mL soil sample is extracted by zonal centrifugation (Hendrickx, 1995). This extraction procedure is based on centrifugation in combination with separation solutions (kaolin and $MgSO_4$) which create separate layers (zones) in the centrifuge chamber. The result is hundreds to thousands of nematodes in a suspension (150 mL) separated from the mineral fraction of the soil. The nematode suspension is reduced until approximately 40 mL after a minimum of 3 hours. During that time nematodes drop to the bottom of the beaker after which 110 mL supernatant was removed.

2.2.2 DNA-extraction experiment

An experiment was set-up containing 6 treatments (Figure 8): a combination of 3 techniques to concentrate the nematode suspension (gravity, freeze-drying and filtration) and 2 DNA-extraction kits to extract and purify the DNA from the nematode suspension (DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit and the DNeasy Powerlyzer Powersoil Kit, Qiagen). The first DNA-extraction kit applies an enzymatic, the second a chemical lysis approach. Each treatment was repeated 5 times. The nematode suspension was obtained from 30 soil samples. The suspensions were all mixed, homogenised and re-divided in equal parts. Before the start of each treatment, the suspensions were spiked with 1 mL of a root-knot nematode culture (*Meloidogyne chiwoodi*; 235 individuals per mL). A nematode species not yet present in the nematode suspensions.

The DNA-yield of all the methods tested, was measured (Quantus fluorometer, Promega). However, measuring the DNA-yield does not provide information about the quality of the DNA. To check whether the DNA can be amplified, a qPCR was performed as well. qPCR (quantitative PCR) is a molecular method able to detect and quantify DNA from a specific organism in a DNA-extract provided that a species-specific DNA-probe and/or primerset exists for the chosen target and the amplification is not inhibited due to low DNA quality. As mentioned before, the nematode suspensions were spiked with *Meloidogyne chitwoodi*. A DNA-probe able to specifically detect this species during a qPCR exists (Zijlstra & Van Hoof, 2006) and was applied.

Figure 8. Scheme of the DNA-extraction experiment.

2.2.3 Suspension experiment

Zonal centrifugation is applied to collect the nematodes from soil samples (Hendrickx, 1995). The volume of the nematode suspensions is reduced till 40 mL after letting the nematodes settle down by gravity force during 3 hours. This step is done to remove most of the kaolin particles which are also but partly collected in the nematode suspension after zonal centrifugation but which need more time to settle down compared to the more heavy nematodes. The gravity-method then further reduces the volume before DNA-extraction while the other (tested) techniques rely on other principles (freeze-drying and filtration). The first concentration step to remove most of the kaolin was retained whatever method was tested in the previous mentioned DNA-extraction experiment because the kaolin can make morphological analysis, preceding the DNA-extraction, more difficult.

During the suspension experiment (Figure 9), we tested whether the best nematode concentration-method (filtration) is still showing satisfactory results when we omit the first step of reducing the suspension volume and thus removing most of the kaolin, and proceed immediately with DNA-extraction. This protocol could be selected when no morphological analysis is planned. As an extra test we remained the step in which the suspension volume is reduced but after waiting 24 hours instead of 3 hours. During that time also most of the kaolin is settled down and thus not removed.

Figure 9. Scheme of the suspension experiment.

2.2.4 Filtration experiment

Figure 10. Scheme of the filtration experiment.

Previous experiments pointed the combination of filtration with the chemical lysis based DNA-extraction kit as the best method. The filter used during the filtration-tests was 0.8 µM PES (PolyEtherSulfon; Supor, PALL Laboratory). This filter provided nice results and therefor there was no immediate need to test other types of filters. However, cheaper filters exist and, more importantly,

we experienced difficulties to order the PES-filters (delivery periods exceeded easily 100 days). Therefore we organized an experiment (Figure 10) in which we applied alternative types of filters: 11 μ M cellulose paper filter (Whatman), 0.8 μ M cellulose acetate (Sartorius Biolab), 1,6 μ M glass fiber filter (VWR European).

2.2.5 Nematode community sequence analysis

A library prep was made from each nematode DNA extract by applying a 2-step amplification process. Amplicon libraries with sample-specific indices were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the instructions provided by the sequence service (Admera Health Biopharma Services, New Jersey, USA) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq PE300 platform (2 x 300 bp). A more detailed description of this procedure can be found in "Handbook - protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis" (Calviño et al., 2020).

After receiving the raw sequence data from the sequence service provider, the data is analysed and quality checked. Obviously we proceeded with the sequence analysis method scoring the best after the tests conducted and described in previous chapter. Briefly, poor quality sequences (70% \geq Q30) were removed. Primer sequences were removed from the sequences using Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014), adapters were removed with cutadapt v3.3 (Martin, 2011), forward and reverse sequences were merged with PEAR v.0.9.11 (Zhang et al., 2014) and the sequences with N's or more than six expected errors were filtered with vsearch v. 2.17.0 (Rognes et al., 2016). DADA2 v1.18 (Callahan et al., 2016) was used to model and correct Illumina-sequenced amplicon errors in the retained sequences. It subsequently infers exactly the sequences into amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and resolves differences of as little as one nucleotide. Chimeric sequences were identified and removed using the consensus method implemented in the DADA2 function `removeBimeraDenovo`. The RDP Naive Bayesian Classifier algorithm (Wang et al., 2007), also implemented in the DADA2 package, was used to assign taxonomic units to the ASVs using an in-house curated custom NCBI reference database (see previous chapter). Finally, the composition and number of genera was counted to reveal the biodiversity on genus level and further compare the DNA-extraction methods.

2.3 Results and discussion

2.3.1 DNA-extraction experiment

The filtration method (0,8 μ M PES filter) combined with the soil DNA-extraction kit based on chemical lysis (DNeasy Powerlyzer Powersoil Kit from Qiagen) gave the highest yield of DNA (Figure 11). The qPCR demonstrated that the same combination resulted in the lowest inhibition or highest sensitivity

(Figure 12). So we can conclude that the filtration-method combined with the soil DNA-extraction kit based on chemical lysis is the best choice, moreover, it is also by far the fastest method.

Figure 11. Mean DNA-concentration of the 6 treatments tested during the DNA-extraction experiment combining 3 concentration techniques and 2 DNA-extraction kits. A & D: gravity-method, B & E: Freeze-drying, C & F: Filtration; A,B & C: Blood & Tissue Kit, D, E & F: Powerlyzer Kit.

Figure 12. Mean CT-values after qPCR (Zijlstra & Van Hoof 2006) and the 6 treatments tested during the DNA-extraction experiment combining 3 concentration techniques and 2 DNA-extraction kits. A & D: gravity-method, B & E: Freeze-drying, C & F: Filtration; A,B & C: Blood & Tissue Kit, D, E & F: Powerlyzer Kit.

2.3.2 Suspension experiment

Again, the soil DNA-extraction kit based on chemical lysis (DNeasy Powerlyzer Powersoil Kit, Qiagen) gave the highest yield of DNA (Figure 13). More importantly, we can conclude that using this method, no preceding removal of the supernatant with most of the kaolin is needed to have a successful DNA-extraction. qPCR confirms this result (Figure 14): ct-values show no significant differences between the 3 treatments of the nematode suspension and detection of *M. chitwoodi* is most sensitive when using the chemical DNA-extraction method.

Figure 13. Mean DNA-concentration of the suspension experiment combining 3 different conditions of the suspension and 2 DNA-extraction kits. A & D: suspension not reduced, B & E: suspension reduced after 3 hours, C & F suspension reduced after 24 hours; A,B & C: Blood & Tissue Kit, D, E & F: Powerlyzer Kit.

Figure 14. Mean CT-values after qPCR (Zijlstra & Van Hoof 2006) and the suspension experiment combining 3 different conditions of the suspension and 2 DNA-extraction kits. A & D: suspension not reduced, B & E: suspension reduced after 3 hours, C & F suspension reduced after 24 hours; A,B & C: Blood & Tissue Kit, D, E & F: Powerlyzer Kit.

2.3.3 Filtration experiment

Figure 15. A. Mean DNA-concentration and B. mean CT-values after qPCR (Zijlstra & Van Hoof 2006) of the filtration experiment testing 3 different filters (CelAc = Cellulose acetate filter, Gfiber = Glass fiber filter, PES = Polyethersulfon filter).

The cellulose paper filter immediately turned out to be unsuitable as an alternative to the PES-filter because during bead-beating temperature increases quickly resulting in a bit of moisture which turned the paper into pulp. Subsequent DNA-extraction was as good as impossible. Data results of this filter are therefore missing.

The glass fiber filter significantly yielded lower amounts of DNA and therefore is not retained as alternative to the PES-filter. The results of the cellulose-acetate filter was not different compared to the PES-filter. The qPCR resulted in more or less the same ct-values for all filters (Figure 15).

To conclude, the cellulose-acetate filter can be used as an alternative to the PES-filter. However, we did not decide to really replace the PES-filter by the cellulose-acetate filter because the latter is almost 100% more expensive. Only in cases the PES-filter cannot be delivered (on time), the cellulose-acetate filter will be ordered and used instead.

2.3.4 Nematode species richness

To have an idea on the efficiency of the 2 different DNA-extraction methods used, the biodiversity of the nematode suspensions from previous mentioned DNA-extraction and suspension experiments was determined as well (Figure 16 en 17). From the results we can conclude that the chemical DNA-extraction method doesn't perform significantly better compared to the enzymatic DNA-extraction method based on number of detected genera (Figure 18 and 19). However, we can see that the chemical DNA-extraction method has detected a few more genera in both experiments.

Figure 16. Composition on genus-level of the nematode suspensions used during the DNA-extraction experiment combining 3 concentration techniques (from left to right) and 2 DNA-extraction kits (upper and lower panel). Different colors represent different nematode genera (the spiked nematode *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* included).

Figure 18. Mean number of genera found in the nematode suspensions used during the DNA-extraction experiment combining 3 concentration techniques (gravity-method, freeze-drying and filtration) and 2 DNA-extraction methods (enzymatic and chemical method).

Figure 19. Mean number of genera found in the nematode suspensions used during the suspension experiment combining 3 suspension treatments (0, 3 and 24 hours of letting the nematodes settle down) and 2 DNA-extraction methods (enzymatic and chemical method).

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When we investigate the results of the mean number of genera found combining the DNA-extraction with different suspension treatments, we can notice that removing the supernatant of the nematode suspension obtained by zonal centrifugation after 3 hours results - although statistically speaking not significantly different from the other results – in the highest 'species' richness (Figure 17 and 19). It is possible that the kaolin, which is not (partially) removed, jeopardizes the subsequent DNA-extraction somehow.

Based on the results we decided to retain the removal of the supernatant from the nematode suspension obtained by zonal centrifugation after 3 hours and proceed with the combined DNA-extraction method of filtration and the chemical lysis method for future analyses of nematode communities in the SoildiverAgro-project (e.g. WP5).

3 Quantification applying correction factors

3.1 Introduction

It has been demonstrated that the frequency of sequence reads representing individual species does not correlate with the absolute number of individuals in a given soil sample (Creer et al., 2010). This lack of correlation is probably caused by a combination of (i) variation in DNA-extraction efficiency for different groups of nematodes (Waeyenberge et al., 2019), (ii) differential primer-binding preferences during PCR amplification (2-step PCR method), (iii) PCR amplification bias (short sequences are amplified preferentially in amplicon mixes of variable length (e.g. ribosomal DNA) and templates of very low or very high GC content amplify less well) (Krehenwinkel et al., 2017), and (iv) the fact that 18S rRNA is a multi-copy gene with a variable number of repeats amongst taxa within the phylum of Nematoda (Bik et al., 2013). As a result, the number of individuals belonging to certain genera are overrated, while others are underrated following DNA-metabarcoding analysis.

A preliminary study with artificial nematode communities suggested that correction factors can improve quantification in DNA-metabarcoding (Waeyenberge et al., 2019). Without correction factors, the DNA-metabarcoding method is applicable to monitor shifts in both nematode species richness and (relative) abundances and hence it can evaluate the effect of anthropogenic treatments in a given experimental set-up or agricultural management system, however, the method cannot evaluate correctly the biodiversity per se due to the incorrectness of relative proportions between certain nematode genera (Darby et al., 2013). Therefore, some tests were planned to increase our insights on this matter to eventually upgrade the DNA-metabarcoding to a quantitatively reliable biodiversity assay.

3.2 Material and Methods

3.2.1 Preparations of mock communities

Two artificial nematode communities were prepared by isolating a number of nematode individuals from different nematode suspensions after morphological characterization on genus (or species)-level by microscopy and by isolating individuals from pure cultures (Table 1). The first mock community was prepared 3 times (Mock1.1, 1.2 and 1.3) with 5 individuals for each taxon in each of the 3 tubes. Mock community 2 (Mock 2) was not repeated but contained 15 individuals for each taxon. Both mock communities were characterized by DNA-metabarcoding as explained in chapter 2.2.5. We prepared the mock communities in such a way that a wide range of different taxa (orders and families) of nematodes are present.

TABLE 1

NR.	GENUS/SPECIES	ORDER/FAMILY	*	ORIGIN
MOCK COMMUNITY 1				
1	<i>Heterodera schachtii</i>	Tylenchida/Heteroderidae	5	Suspension 1
2	<i>Criconema annuliferum</i>	Tylenchida/Criconematidae	5	Suspension 2
3	<i>Macroposthonia xenoplax</i> (syn. <i>Mesocriconema xenoplax</i>)	Tylenchida/Criconematidae	5	Suspension 2
4	<i>Wilsonema otophorum</i>	Plectida/Plectidae	5	Suspension 3
5	<i>Anaplectus porosus</i>	Plectida/Plectidae	5	Suspension 4
6	<i>Mononchus tridentatus</i> (syn. <i>Anatonchus tridentatus</i>)	Mononchida/Mononchidae	5	Suspension 4
7	<i>Oigolaimella</i> sp.	Rhabditida/Diplogastridae	5	Culture 1
8	<i>Mesorhabditis spiculigera</i>	Rhabditida/Rhabditidae	5	Culture 2
9	<i>Pratylenchus penetrans</i>	Tylenchida/Pratylenchidae	5	Culture 3
MOCK COMMUNITY 2				
1	<i>Xiphinema</i> sp.	Dorylaimida/Longidoridae	15	Suspension 3
2	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp.	Tylenchida/Tylenchulidae	15	Suspension 4
3	<i>Rotylenchus</i> sp.	Tylenchida/Hoplolaimidae	15	Suspension 4
4	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	Enoplida/Alaimidae	15	Suspension 5
5	<i>Butlerius</i> sp.	Diplogastrida/Diplogastridae	15	Culture 4
6	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Tylenchida/Heteroderidae	15	Suspension 6
7	<i>Cuticularia</i> sp. (<i>Poikilolaimus</i> sp.)	Rhabditida/Rhabditidae	15	Culture 5
8	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp.	Tylenchida/Aphelenchidae	15	Culture 6
9	<i>Pratylenchus penetrans</i>	Tylenchida/Pratylenchidae	15	Culture 3
10	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Tylenchida/Meloidogynidae	15	Culture 7
11	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Rhabditida/Aphelenchoididae	15	Culture 8
12	<i>Cephalobus</i> sp. (<i>Acrobeloides</i>)	Rhabditida/Cephalobidae	15	Suspension 5
13	<i>Meso- or Prodorylaimus</i> sp.	Dorylaimida/Dorylaimidae	15	Suspension 5
14	<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.	Tylenchida/Tylenchidae	15	Suspension 3

Table 1. Composition of the mock communities prepared to determine correction factors after comparison with DNA-metabarcoding data (* = number of individuals).

3.2.2 Characterization of natural nematode suspensions morphologically and molecularly

Although mock communities are believed to provide correction factors to estimate better the relative quantification of the community composition (Waeyenberge et al., 2019), the downside is that artificially obtained communities cannot mimic a real, highly diverse, community. Therefore, it was decided to investigate in parallel to what extent correction factors can be defined by using real nematode communities with a known species composition. For this purpose we characterized 'natural' nematode communities both morphologically as molecularly by DNA-metabarcoding. However, as mentioned before, characterizing nematode communities is extremely time-consuming. Therefore, we focused on a number of plant-parasitic nematode genera because they are more easily recognized within a diverse nematode community due to the presence of a typical stylet used by these nematodes to feed on plant cells and because of our expertise on this particular group. Moreover, it has been mentioned before that plant-feeding nematodes (Tylenchida) are underrated after DNA-metabarcoding compared to morphological analyses and thus are suitable as a test subject (Treonis et al., 2018.)

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 Correction factors based on mock communities

Molecular analysis could detect all but one family used to prepare the mock communities. In mock community 2 only family Alaimidae was not detected, instead another family (Belonidiridae) was annotated not used to prepare the mock community. Both families however belong to the same Class (Enoplea). In mock communities 1.1 till 1.3 additional families were detected. It has been noticed before that low numbers of nematodes (<100; total number of nematodes in the mock 1 communities is 45, total number of nematodes in the mock 2 communities is 210) tends to result in a larger number of taxa. As the concentration of chemicals performing the DNA-amplification is optimized to be used for nematode suspensions with usually a few hundred till thousands of individuals, it is possible that the number of mistakes made during the amplification is increasing when much smaller number of individuals are used resulting in unwanted sequences and thus taxa in the data set.

After analyzing the data, we can conclude that it will be needed to determine correction factors at the level of genera. In table 2 we can notice that different families of the same order show different correction factors but also within one family sometimes we can notice different correction factors. For example the family Heteroderidae was represented by the genus *Heterodera* in mock community 1 (correction factor between 0,6 and 0,9) and *Globodera* in mock community 2 (correction factor of 1,9). The families Diplogastridae and Pratylenchidae were represented by the same genus in both mock communities (*Oigolaimella* and *Pratylenchus* respectively) and resulted in more or less the

same correction factor. So we can conclude that creating correction factors can help to improve quantification, however since they have to be determined on genus level, it is not practically feasible.

TABLE 2

	ORDER/FAMILY	MOCK 1.1	MOCK 1.2	MOCK 1.3	MOCK 2
1	Diplogastrida/Diplogastridae	0,37	0,34	0,39	0,32
2	Dorylaimida/Belondiridae	NA	NA	NA	1,76
3	Dorylaimida/Dorylaimidae	NA	NA	NA	2,33
4	Dorylaimida/Longidoridae	NA	NA	NA	0,87
5	Mononchida/Mononchidae	1,00	0,92	0,68	NA
6	Plectida/Plectidae	1,46	1,01	1,01	NA
7	Rhabditida/Aphelenchoididae	NA	NA	NA	0,34
8	Rhabditida/Cephalobidae	NA	NA	NA	1,24
9	Rhabditida/Rhabditidae	NA	41,75	38,52	0,55
10	Tylenchida/Aphelenchidae	NA	NA	NA	1,33
11	Tylenchida/Criconematidae	1,12	1,55	1,46	NA
12	Tylenchida/Heteroderidae	0,58	0,83	0,90	1,88
13	Tylenchida/Hoplolaimidae	NA	NA	NA	2,11
14	Tylenchida/Meloidogynidae	NA	NA	NA	3,73
15	Tylenchida/Pratylenchidae	2,52	2,22	2,27	3,26
16	Tylenchida/Tylenchidae	NA	NA	NA	2,76
17	Tylenchida/Tylenchulidae	NA	NA	NA	2,02

Table 2. List of correction factors (CR) calculated for the respective nematode families in each of the mock communities prepared. . NA = the correction factor could not be calculated as the respective taxon was not present in the community.

3.3.2 Correction factors based on 'natural' nematode suspensions

Twenty nematode communities were investigated morphologically. The total number of individuals in these communities was 82895. The number of 10 plant-parasitic nematode genera covering 8 families (21428 individuals) was determined morphologically. Genera from four families turned out to be absent or present only in very few number of individuals (<3) and therefore were not further investigated. The relative number of individuals and sequence reads of the following retained families was compared: Pratylenchidae (genus *Pratylenchus*), Heteroderidae (genera *Heterodera* plus *Globodera*), Anguinidae (genus *Ditylenchus*) and Paratylenchidae (genus *Paratylenchus*). Correction factors were calculated on family level, except for Anguinidae. For this family, the correction factor could not be determined as molecular analysis revealed the presence of several non-plant-parasitic genera belonging to this family. These non-plant-parasitic genera were not analysed morphologically.

Therefore, for Anguinidae, the correction factor for separately the genus *Ditylenchus* was determined.

Comparing the (relative) nematode individual counts with sequence reads abundances derived from the DNA-metabarcoding analysis (Table 3), demonstrated over- or underrating of the investigated plant-parasitic nematode families or genera in the molecular analysis. Also we can notice a strong variation in calculated correction factors within one nematode family (e.g. ranging between 0,89 till 6,17 for the family Pratylenchidae). The latter can be due to differences in results between nematode genera or species belonging to this family but it also remains important to take into account the fact that determine the number of all nematodes belonging to one family or genus ranging from a few till thousands of individuals within very divers and complex nematode suspensions is delicate even for a specialist. Missing individuals is easy but this number can represent a rather large portion when only a dozen of individuals are present in the suspension. Therefore, to determine correction factors, using mock communities with known numbers of nematode individuals assembled remains the better way (easier, more feasible and probably more correct).

TABLE 3

	A	B	CR FAM. PRATY- LENCHIDAE	CR FAM. HETERO- DERIDAE	CR GENUS <i>DITYLENCH</i> <i>US</i>	CR FAM. PARATY- LENCHIDAE
1	885	17036	3,33	0,30	Undetermined	Undetermined
2	3123	4981	1,90	0,33	0,01	Undetermined
3	2441	11311	3,00	Undetermined	Undetermined	Undetermined
4	2851	7979	1,87	0,20	Undetermined	0,01
5	4955	21791	5,97	1,13	0,03	Undetermined
6	3164	16099	5,57	1,74	Undetermined	Undetermined
7	2025	59358	3,87	0,07	Undetermined	0,03
8	3060	25554	4,79	0,19	Undetermined	0,31
9	2386	83252	5,83	10,11	0,06	0,80
10	2141	43402	4,12	Undetermined	0,04	0,26
11	8749	16777	3,39	Undetermined	0,06	0,30
12	4557	6183	2,02	Undetermined	Undetermined	Undetermined
13	3034	77688	3,86	9,31	Undetermined	0,23
14	4815	14989	2,17	Undetermined	Undetermined	0,23
15	13140	18311	4,24	0,98	0,24	Undetermined
16	8349	29880	3,67	0,68	0,12	1,08
17	3268	29531	6,17	2,19	0,39	Undetermined
18	2028	35432	0,89	Undetermined	0,59	1,70
19	2844	143260	3,67	Undetermined	0,98	Undetermined
20	5080	52329	3,59	Undetermined	0,06	0,64

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Table 3. List of correction factors (CR) calculated for the respective nematode families in each of the 20 investigated nematode communities. A = Total number of nematode individuals counted microscopically, B = total number of sequence reads determined after DNA-metabarcoding. Undetermined = the correction factor could not be calculated because the morphological and/or molecular result was zero.

4 Conclusions

Deliverable report D4.2 describes how a couple of steps in the procedure were tackled to obtain a more accurate application of DNA-metabarcoding for the characterization of nematode communities from soil samples for soil health assessments. This was decided in order to be able to reliably replace the time-consuming morphological characterization of nematode communities. This replacement is important because the traditional morphological analysis is not only extremely time-consuming and thus expensive, it also requires a high level of expertise. Expertise that is getting more difficult to find as training in taxonomy becomes rare, and many students or lab technicians prefer to avoid hours of routine microscopy work.

During WP4, the following objectives were obtained. Firstly, a curated database of 18S rRNA nematode sequences was constructed from available databases. The curated database was further expanded with nematode genera/families still missing or being less represented by targeted sampling and combined pheno- and genotypic characterisation. The database finally contains more than 5100 sequences belonging to 758 genera and 1676 species. Secondly, different bio-informatics pipelines were compared and the one most efficient for reliable nematode taxonomic assignments, that is linking the obtained unknown nematode sequences from a nematode community extracted from a soil sample with the correct known sequences (and thus nematode identifications) available in the sequence database by comparison, was selected. Not only mock-communities (communities artificially made to know their exact composition) were used, also natural nematode communities were investigated because mock communities can never resemble the complexity of a natural nematode community. Thirdly, the DNA-extraction of nematode suspensions derived from soil samples was optimized. It was demonstrated that from certain nematode taxa no or less amount of DNA could be extracted by the DNA-extraction methods available. Probably the variable compositions of the nematode's cuticula in relation to their lifestyle can explain this. Our experiments demonstrated that the combination of filtration under vacuum, bead beating of the filter holding the nematode community, combined with a DNA-extraction kit applying a chemical lysis and including several washing steps to obtain purified DNA, turned out to be the most effective DNA-extraction method for nematode suspensions extracted from soil samples as determined by DNA-yield and nematode 'species' richness. Fourthly, attempts to improve the quantitative aspect of DNA-metabarcoding were executed. The frequency of sequence reads representing individual species does not correlate with the absolute number of individuals in a given soil sample. This lack of correlation is probably caused by a combination of factors but can be 'corrected' by means of correction factors. Although we hoped to set correction factors on the level of an order or family, it turned out that it is necessary to determine correction factors at the level of a nematode genus, which is due to the huge number of nematode genera practically unfeasible. As a consequence, DNA-metabarcoding is only used to compare results of different samples (biodiversity change tracking/monitoring) instead of assessing the exact biodiversity of separate samples.

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All the obtained optimizations were implemented into our DNA-metabarcoding protocol. This resulted into a more reliable method able to replace the morphological characterizations.

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ANNEXES-tables

TABLE A1

NR.	MORFOLOGICAL IDENTIFICATION	MOLECULAR CONFIRMATION	REMARK
1	<i>Hemicycliophora thienemanni</i>		
2	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>		
3	<i>Xiphinema diversicaudatum</i>		
4	<i>Paratylenchus nanus</i>		
5	<i>Mylonchulus sigmaturus</i>		
6	<i>Trichodorus variopapillatus</i>		
7	<i>Mesocriconema annulata</i>		
8	<i>Criconema annuliferum</i>		
9	<i>Anaplectus granulatus</i>		
10	<i>Plectus</i> sp.		
11	<i>Enchodelus macrodorus</i> syn. <i>Allodorylaimus</i>		
12	<i>Prodorylaimus</i> sp.		
13	<i>Longidorus elongatus</i>		
14	<i>Anatonchus tridentatus</i>		
15	<i>Anatonchus tridentatus</i>		
16	<i>Filenchus thornei</i>		Closely related
17	<i>Prodorylaimus acris</i>		
18	<i>Rotylenchus robustus</i>		
19	<i>Tripyla filicaudata</i>		
20	<i>Allodiplogaster sudhausi</i> syn. <i>Diplenteron colobocercus</i>		
21	<i>Cruzinema (tripartitum)</i>		
22	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>		
23	<i>Tylenchus (arcuatus?</i> => juveniel)		
24	<i>Rotylenchus robustus</i>		
25	<i>Labronema vulvapapillatum</i>		Closely related
26	<i>Prismatolaimus dolichurus</i>		
27	<i>Bastiania gracilis (longicaudata)</i>		
28	<i>Teratocephalus terrestris (tenuis)</i>		
29	<i>Miconchus</i> sp.		Closely related
30	<i>Aporcelaimus</i> sp. (<i>regius</i>)		
31	<i>Acrobeloides buetschlii</i>		Closely related
32	<i>Bitylenchus maximus</i>		
33	<i>Acrobeles mariannae</i>		
34	<i>Merlinius microdorus</i> or <i>brevidens</i>		
35	<i>Aporcelaimellus</i> sp.		
36	<i>Nygolaimus loofi</i>		

37	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	Green	
38	<i>Bastiana gracilis</i>	Yellow	Low quality sequence
39	<i>Paratripyla intermedia</i>	Grey	
40	<i>Anaplectus granulosus</i>	Green	
41	<i>Pelodera cystilarva Völk</i>	Red	
42	<i>Meloidogyne hapla</i>	Green	
43	<i>Cervidellus serratus</i>	Grey	
44	<i>Trischistoma (monhystera)</i>	Grey	
45	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	Yellow	Closely related
46	<i>Thonus labi</i>	Red	
47	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>	Green	
48	<i>Bunonema reticulatum</i>	Green	
49	<i>Wilsonema schuurmansstekhoveni</i>	Grey	
50	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	Green	
51	<i>Cephalobus sp.</i>	Yellow	Closely related
52	<i>Rhabditis belari = Mesorhabditis belari</i>	Green	
53	<i>Rhabditophanes sp.</i>	Green	
54	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	Red	
55	<i>Plectus acuminatus</i>	Green	
56	<i>Eudorylaimus iners?</i>	Red	
57	<i>Bitylenchus dubius</i>	Green	
58	<i>Allodorylaimus or Eudorylaimus sp.?</i>	Red	
59	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	Green	
60	<i>Mononchus truncatus?</i>	Green	
61	<i>Longidorus vineacola</i>	Green	
62	<i>Plectus parvus</i>	Green	
63	<i>Miconchus sp.</i>	Green	
64	Dorylaimidae	Grey	

Table A1. List of newly retrieved 18S rRNA sequences from morphologically identified nematode individuals. The sequences were blasted with NCBI Genbank to confirm the morphological identification. Green = morphological and molecular identification are in agreement; yellow = morphological and molecular identification are not in agreement with possible explanation (remark); red = morphological and molecular identification are not in agreement; grey = morphological identification could not be confirmed by the molecular method